
94. The mass of the Local Group

IN MY PREVIOUS ESSAY, I looked at the how the Gaia astrometry, and in particular the kinematics of globular cluster and local group dwarf spheroidal galaxies, are providing an improvement in our estimates of the mass of our Galaxy. I will continue here on the related question of the total mass of the Local Group.

The ‘Local Group’, a term introduced by Edwin Hubble in 1936, is an ‘overdensity’ of around 80 known galaxies, extending across some 3 Mpc, and dominated by the Milky Way and Andromeda (M31). Both are spiral galaxies with masses of order $10^{12}M_{\odot}$, and both are accompanied by their own systems of smaller satellite galaxies, including many ‘ultra-faint’ dwarf spheroidals.

In the case of our Galaxy, these include the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds, along with Sagittarius, Draco, Carina, Sextans, Fornax, and many others. Tied to Andromeda are M32, M110, NGC 147, and many others. A more complete list of known members, and some illustrative graphics, are included at this [wiki page](#).

OVER THE PAST 20 years, much new insight has been gained about the evolution and merger history of our own Galaxy, specifically as it ‘devoured’ smaller nearby galaxies over its multi-billion year history.

Gaia is helping to clarify the picture, revealing various debris streams, including the Gaia–Enceladus and Milky Way merger some 10 Gyr ago which contributed to the formation of our Galaxy’s thick disk (Helmi et al., 2018), and the ‘phase-space spiral’ attributed to a recent crossing of our Galaxy’s disk by the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy 300–900 Myr ago (Antoja et al., 2018).

In the case of Andromeda, a dominant merger some 2 Gyr ago has been proposed to explain its compact and metal-rich satellite M32 as the stripped core of the disrupted satellite, as well its rotating inner stellar halo, and its associated giant stellar stream (D’Souza & Bell, 2018).

In any successful cosmological model, all of these, and many other properties of the Local Group, must also be consistent with the increasingly detailed predictions of large-scale numerical models of the formation and evolution of structure in the Universe.

AS I OUTLINED in essay #93, the mass of the Local Group can be estimated, along with that of our own Galaxy, by modelling the kinematics of various ‘tracer’ objects (notably halo stars, satellite galaxies and globular clusters) around its most prominent members.

Underpinning these methods are various assumptions tied to our presently favoured cosmological models, for example, that the dark matter is clustered around the major galaxies, and not distributed more uniformly throughout the Local Group.

Indeed one of the early triumphs of the Λ CDM (Lambda cold dark matter) cosmological model in the 1990s was its prediction that massive galaxies like the Milky Way should be surrounded by many dark matter dominated satellite halos, which were only discovered in the predicted numbers over the past 20 years (essay #31).

Other ‘tensions’ with respect to Λ CDM have been noted over the past few years as the accuracies of relevant observations improve. A detailed compilation is provided by Perivolaropoulos & Skara (2022).

Amongst these, which I mention as perhaps one of the easiest to appreciate, is the ‘too-big-to-fail’ problem (Boylan-Kolchin et al., 2011), an inconsistency between the predicted mass of dark matter sub-haloes in Λ CDM theory, and the observed central mass of the brightest satellite galaxies in the Local Group.

For these and other reasons, mass estimates of the Local Group (amongst various other observables) continue to provide a powerful test of cosmological models.

TWO OF THE MOST developed methods for determining the mass of the Local Group are via cosmological simulations, and via the so-called ‘timing method’.

The former infers the Galaxy’s total mass by comparing model satellites in (for example) the EAGLE cosmological hydrodynamics simulations with the dynamics of a number of the ‘classical’ Milky Way satellites with six-dimensional phase-space measurements (i.e. positions and velocities), most recently including updated proper motions from Gaia (including the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds, Draco, and Ursa Minor).

The timing method, which I introduced in essay #93, is based on the hypothesis that the Milky Way and M31 proto-galaxies had a small separation at the time of the Big Bang, subsequently moving apart as they participated in the Hubble flow. Given an estimate of the age of the Universe, together with their present separation and approach velocity, the equations of motion can be solved to give the mass of the Galaxy, along with that of the Local Group.

The timing method has been progressively refined since its original formulation by Kahn & Woltjer (1959), who assumed, for example, that the Milky Way and M31 are on an exactly radial orbit. Einasto & Lynden-Bell (1982), later showed that the problem retained an analytic solution even if M31 has some tangential motion.

Since then, numerous details have been refined, including the tidal effects of galaxies beyond the Local Group; the introduction of a cosmological constant, which contributes an additional expansion term, and increases the Local Group mass by some 10%; and the effects of hierarchical growth of both galaxies by comparisons with cosmological simulations.

OF SPECIFIC INTEREST here are the latest refinements of the orbit of M31, and indeed M33, as a result of the improving observational accuracy of their tangential motions, most recently using Gaia DR2 (van der Marel et al., 2019). They determined the proper motions of a number of massive stars in each galaxy, relative to surrounding background quasars, to derive a centre-of-mass proper motion of $(65 \pm 18, -57 \pm 15) \mu\text{arcsec yr}^{-1}$ for M31 (1084 stars), and $(31 \pm 19, -29 \pm 16) \mu\text{arcsec yr}^{-1}$ for M33 (1518 stars), highlighting ‘*the future potential of Gaia for proper motion studies beyond the Milky Way*’.

Similar values for M31 were determined from Gaia EDR3 by Salomon et al. (2021), who noted that their values were consistent with (but more accurate than) earlier Hubble Space Telescope measurements that predicted a future merger between Andromeda and our Milky Way Galaxy (Sohn et al., 2012).

IN A SUBSEQUENT development, Benisty et al. (2022) adjusted the approach velocity between the Milky Way and M31 for the effects of our Galaxy’s motion towards the Large Magellanic Cloud.

They gave two estimates of the total mass of the Local Group: $3.4^{+1.4}_{-1.1} \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ when using a higher tangential velocity for M31 of 80 km s^{-1} , and $3.1^{+1.3}_{-1.0} \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ when using a lower value of 60 km s^{-1} . This can be compared with a *known* mass of $3.7^{+0.5}_{-0.5} \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$, based on the likely mass of the four most substantial members (the Milky Way, M31, M33 and the LMC), with the minor members contributing about $0.7 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$.

MUST MAKE another aside. The Large Magellanic Cloud is the most massive satellite galaxy of the Milky Way, at more than a tenth of our Galaxy’s mass. Just past its closest approach of about 50 kpc, and passing the Milky Way at more than 300 km s^{-1} , this ‘fly-by’ is affecting our Galaxy in various ways... including dislodging the Milky Way disk from the Galactic centre of mass!

Petersen & Peñarrubia (2021) used Gaia DR2 data to show that the Milky Way disk is moving with respect to stellar tracers in the outer halo, at about 32 km s^{-1} , and in a direction that points to an earlier location on the trajectory of the Large Magellanic Cloud.

The timing method, I recall, rests on modeling the relative orbit of our Galaxy and M31. And this will be affected by any perturbation of our Galaxy’s equilibrium, including this recent pericentric passage of the LMC, along with any by-products of its merger history.

Accounting for this perturbation of the Milky Way disk lowers the inferred Local Group mass by 10–20% compared to a static halo. Specifically, Chamberlain et al. (2022) gave an updated total mass of between $4.0^{+0.5}_{-0.3} \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ or $4.5^{+0.8}_{-0.6} \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ depending on their adopted kinematic measurements of M31.

SLOWLY BUT SURELY, and in numerous ways, Gaia is contributing to our understanding of the Local Group, its total mass, and its implications for cosmology.